

»To advocate for positive change in the policies, culture, and environment that affect the quality of training, well-being, and employment conditions of early career researchers«

Eurodoc

Annual Report

2024/25

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Board for the Eurodoc Administration 2024/2025

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eurodoc

The European Council of Doctoral
Candidates and Junior Researchers

Foreword

It is a difficult task to write a summary of the highlights of this year in Eurodoc: It has been a year both with a lot of activities driven from within Eurodoc, but also a year where Eurodoc has had to respond to several European agendas. Topics like the EU's 10th Framework program, its Multi Financial Framework and the upcoming European Research Act have dominated the European agenda alongside attacks on academic freedom and democratic backsliding.

Throughout the year, Eurodoc has put focus on how precariousness is a multifaceted problem and how similarly to equitable opportunities an intersectional approach is needed. A common failing within the sector is to fully acknowledge how precarious the research and academic career is compared to other career paths within the public and private sector for holders of master degrees. To address this issue, Eurodoc in the spring 2025 adopted the position "[Eurodoc Statement on Employment and Financial Conditions of ECRs](#)" which states that the starting salary of doctoral candidates should be similar to that of upper secondary teachers. This position allows for a benchmark across Europe on whether the salary level of doctoral candidates are competitive or not.

Furthermore, Eurodoc is involved in key European initiatives. In fall 2024, Eurodoc was invited by COST to chair their cross cutting action (CCA) on research careers. In CoARA, Eurodoc continues to ensure a strong focus on early career researchers in the context of a reform of research assessment and co-chairs the working group on early and mid career researchers. In June 2025 Eurodoc released its [Report on the Eurodoc Postdoc survey](#). Though the data is from 2018-2019, it remains relevant as data on postdocs' situation still remain scarce and depressingly little has changed.

Globally Academic Freedom is under attack, something that has become blatantly more clear this past year. Eurodoc has a strong focus on promoting and advocating for academic values such as academic freedom, institutional autonomy and the participation of the academic community in governance and as such had. In connection to this, the [Eurodoc ValDem 2025 Ambassador program](#) provides a comprehensive overview of the democratic values of higher education and research in Europe.

Eurodoc has in 2024/2025 put focus on the importance of the inclusion of early career researchers in the governance of higher education institutions, the challenges they face when it comes to representation within higher education institutions and public authorities, and how to strengthen their participation in the governance of higher education. To put focus on this topic, Eurodoc adopted the statement "[Eurodoc Statement on Representational Rights of ECRs](#)" addressing the importance of ensuring representational rights of doctoral candidates and other ECRs. Furthermore, in the policy paper "[Eurodoc Statement on Doctoral Supervision](#)" Eurodoc outlines its opinions on supervision in doctoral education.

The 2024 World Science Forum took place in Budapest, Hungary, where Eurodoc actively contributed by co-organizing two side events with YAE, ICoRSA, and MCAA, and participating in two external panels. Eurodoc also engaged in shaping the Forum's final declaration.

Finally, we wish to mention the Campaign Ukrainian Scientists. In this campaign more than 20 ECRs from Ukraine have been interviewed about their research and how the war has affected their research.

Eurodoc Administrative Board Members 2024/2025

Pil Maria Saugmann, Nicola Dengo, Manca Lunder, Hannah Schoch,
Norbert Bencze, Karl Kilbo Edlund, and Magali Weisgerber

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1 Eurodoc Objectives

Eurodoc shall pursue the following objectives according our [statute](#), [mission and vision](#):

- (a) **To represent** doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level in matters of education, research and professional development of their careers.
- (b) **To advance** the quality of doctoral programmes and the standards of research activity in Europe.
- (c) **To promote** the circulation of information on issues regarding young researchers, **organize** events, **take part** in debates, and **assist** in the elaboration of policies about Higher Education and Research in Europe.
- (d) **To establish** and **promote** cooperation between national associations representing doctoral candidates and junior researchers within Europe. Eurodoc shall not interfere with the competences of its member organisations in respect of all national matters and issues.

2 Eurodoc Members & Observers

2.1 National Associations (NAs)

Belgium (PhD society), Croatia (Penkala), Czech Republic (SK RVŠ), Denmark (PAND), Finland (FUURT), France (CJC), Germany (THESIS), Hungary (DOSZ), Ireland (IFUT and USI), Italy (ADI), Latvia (LJZA), Lithuania (LSYR), Netherlands (PNN), Norway (SiN), Poland (KRD), Portugal (ABIC), Romania (ANOSR), Slovakia (ADS), Slovenia (MA), Spain (FJI-Precarios), Sweden (SNPA and SFS/SFSDK), Switzerland (actionuni), Ukraine (YSC), and Azerbaijan (AYSPMU)

Fig. 1 Eurodoc's Members and Observers on a map

3 Eurodoc Administration Members and External Representatives

The Eurodoc administration consists of the Administrative board, Secretariat and Advisory board members.

3.1 Administrative Board

Position	Person	Association
President	Pil Maria Saugmann	Sweden/SFS/SFSDK/SNPA
Vice-President	Nicola Dengo	Italy/ADI
Treasurer	Manca Lunder	Slovenia/MZDA
Secretary	Hannah Schoch	Switzerland/actionuni
General Board Member	Norbert Bencze	Hungary/DOSZ
General Board Member	Karl Kilbo Edlund	Sweden/SFS/SFSDK
General Board Member	Magali Weissgerber	France/CJC

3.2 Secretariat

Position	Person	Association
Secretariat Coordinator	Linnéa Carlsson	Sweden/SFS/SFSDK
External Communication Coordinator	Anna Pavelieva	Ukraine/YSC
Newsletter Coordinator	Viktoriiia Lemeshchenko	Ukraine/YSC
French Language Officers	Magali Weissgerber	France/CJC
Webmaster	Khrystyna Zub	Ukraine/YSC
WG Doctoral Training Coordinator	Laura Weihl	Denmark/PAND
	Anthony Waked	Belgium/PSL
WG Research Careers and Working Conditions Coordinator	Anastasiia Simakhova	Ukraine/YSC
WG Mental Health Coordinator	Aleksandra Levandowska	Poland/KRD
	Sara Willhammar	Sweden/ SFS/SFSDK
WG Open Science Coordinator		
WG AI & AI Coordinator	Agnieszka Zyra*	Eurodoc
	Pil Maria Saugmann*	Sweden/SFS/SFSDK
WG Equitable Opportunities and Sustainable research Cultures Coordinator	Norbert Bencze	Hungary/DOSZ

3.3 Advisory Board, Auditors, and Procurator

Position	Person	Country
Advisory Board	Oleksandr Berezko	Ukraine
Advisory Board	Sebastian Dahle	German/Slovenia
Advisory Board	Miia Ijäs-Idrobo	Finland
Advisory Board	Beata Zwierzyńska	Poland
Auditor (2024/2025-2025/2026)	Topias Tolonen	Sweden, SFS/SFS-DK
Auditor (2024/2025)	Claudia Dobrinski	Germany, Thesis EV
Procurator	Mathias Schroijen	Belgium

3.4 Eurodoc Taskforces

VALDEM		
<i>This task force has conceptualised and organised Eurodoc's Ambassador Programme for Values and Democracy in European Research and Higher Education.</i>	Hannah Schoch	Eurodoc
	Norbert Bencze	Eurodoc
	Pil Maria Saugmann	Eurodoc
25ECRs		
<i>This taskforce has been formed for the conceptualisation and the organisation Eurodoc's 25th anniversary.</i>	Agnieszka Zyra	Former President of Eurodoc
	Eva Hnatkova	Former President of Eurodoc
	Gareth O'Neill	Former President of Eurodoc
	Mathias Schroijen	Former Secretary of Eurodoc
	Pil Maria Saugmann	President of Eurodoc

3.5 Eurodoc Project Involvement

Project	Person	Role
DRU	Hannah Schoch	<i>Expert</i>
	Pil Maria Saugmann*	<i>Formal contact point, Expert</i>
IANUS	Hannah Schoch*	<i>Formal contact point, Expert</i>
	Linnea Carlsson	<i>Expert</i>
OPEN4UA	Agnieszka Zyra*	<i>Formal contact point, Expert</i>
OPTIMA		<i>Pil Maria Saugmann*</i>
OPUS	Agnieszka Zyra	Project officer
	Pil Maria Saugmann	<i>Expert</i>
	Sebastian Dahle*	<i>Formal contact point, Expert</i>

ORE	Nicola Dengo	<i>Expert</i>
	Pil Maria Saugmann	<i>Formal contact point, Expert</i>
SECURE	Gledson Emidio	Project officer
	Pil Maria Saugmann	<i>Expert</i>
	Sebastian Dahle*	<i>Formal contact point, Expert</i>
SECURE2	Nicola Dengo	<i>Expert</i>
	Pil Maria Saugmann*	<i>Formal contact point, Expert</i>

3.6 Eurodoc External Representatives

List of representational positions for representation vis-à-vis intergovernmental organisations, in stakeholder groups etc. See section 5.1 for details on the stakeholders/positions.

Position	Person	Mission Area
BFUG	Aleksandra Lewandowska	Higher Education & Doctoral Education
Co-chair CoARA WG EMRC	Sebastian Dahle	Research & Researchers Career
Co-chair CoARA WG EMRC	Magali Weissgerber	Research & Researchers Career
Co-chair CoARA WG ERIP + EMRC	Pil Maria Saugmann	Research & Researchers Career
CD-EDU Bureau	Pil Maria Saugmann	Higher Education & Doctoral Education
CD-EDU Subgroup on HE	Pil Maria Saugmann	Higher Education & Doctoral Education
CD-EDU Subgroup on draft recommendations on history education	Pil Maria Saugmann	Higher Education & Doctoral Education
CD-EDU Working group on Automatic Recognition	Hannah Schoch	Higher Education & Doctoral Education
CINGO Committee (Inclusive territories, environment and health)	Magali Weissgerber	Science and Society
CINGO Committee (Education and Democracy)	Pil Maria Saugmann	Science and Society
CINGO Committee (Gender Equality)	Norbert Bencze	Science and Society
COST CCA Co-chair	Nicola Dengo	Research & Researchers Career
COST CCA Co-chair	Joanna Rutkowska	Research & Researchers Career
ERA Action 5	Sara Pilia	Research & Researchers Career
ERA Stakeholder group 4	Nicola Dengo	Research & Researchers Career
ERA Stakeholder group 4	Pil Maria Saugmann	Research & Researchers Career

ISE WG HE	Linnea Carlsson	Research & Researchers Career
ISE WG HE	Sebastian Dahle	Research & Researchers Career
ISE WG EMCR	Nicola Dengo	Research & Researchers Career
ISE WG EMCRA	Joanna Rutkowska	Research & Researchers Career
MSCA Conference committee	Pil Maria Saugmann	Research & Researchers Career
MSCA Guidelines for Supervision	Karl Kilbo Edlund	Higher Education & Doctoral Education
OING Representation	Manca Lunder	Science and Society

4 Eurodoc Organisational Work

Eurodoc is an organisation run by volunteers. We endeavour to support one another and respect each other's time limits. Thus it is important to prioritise the projects we take on based on their importance for Eurodoc's mission and vision and based on where we think the greatest impact for improving the careers and conditions of early career researchers can be achieved.

5.1 Meetings in Eurodoc

In 2024/2025 the board met monthly. The meetings have alternated between closed and open for the entire organisation. In addition to the board, the external communications officer and the secretariat coordinator have participated in the closed meetings, others by invitation. The president, vice-president, and secretary held working meetings on average bi-weekly and the president, vice-president and treasurer met on average once per month. The president and vice-president has met regularly with Eurodoc's close collaborators.

The open meetings have had the form of National Association meetings. In these, the board of Eurodoc has provided short updates on projects, decisions, and finances followed by specific topics that should be discussed by all the NAs. The board has held **5 NA meetings**; one in September, one in November, one in February, one in April, and one in June. In 2023/2024, the board of Eurodoc replaced the annual questionnaire with individual meetings with the NAs; this practice continued in 2024/2025 a separate presentation will be given at the AGM.

Need to:

- [5 closed meetings](#). This has been achieved.
- [5 open meetings for the entire organisation](#). This has been achieved.

Nice to:

- [Individual meetings with all the NAs](#). This has been achieved.
- [Develop guide and handover documents](#) This has been achieved.
- [A comprehensive update of the vision and mission statement of Eurodoc](#).

Other:

- [Code of Conduct](#)

5.2 Financial Plan

Eurodoc is currently in a financial situation that allows for the administrative board to meet in person, to participate regularly in meetings in Brussels and Strasbourg, and to financially support the Conference and AGM. Without new funding, the prognosis is that Eurodoc could maintain this level of activity for 3 years. However, most financing comes from funded projects and partnerships. Thus, to maintain the level of expenses new income sources are regularly needed. The administrative board of Eurodoc has developed a financial strategy to ensure maintenance of the current level of activities.

Need to:

- [Identify the financial tasks](#). This is addressed in Eurodoc's Financial Report.
- [To provide the AGM 2025 with recommendations on the distributions between different funding types](#). This is addressed in Eurodoc Financial Strategy.
- [To provide the AGM 2025 with a recommendation on if Eurodoc could organise the conference and AGM alone](#). This is addressed in Eurodoc Financial Strategy.

Nice to:

- [To provide an estimate for the annual cost to permanently employ a full time employee in Brussels and a timeline for when this would be possible and what the responsibilities of the employee would be](#). This is addressed in Eurodoc Financial Strategy.

5.3 Working Groups in Eurodoc 2024/2025

The general goals of the working groups (WG) are to raise awareness and propose policy recommendations, encourage wider and systematic data collection, to suggest potential strategies and good practices. The board of Eurodoc proposes 6 working groups for the 2024/2025 term:

- WG Doctoral Training
- WG Mental Health
- WG Open Science
- WG Equitable Opportunities and Sustainable Research Cultures
- WG Career Paths and Working Conditions
- WG Academic Integrity and Artificial Intelligence

The AGM has been provided with an internal report from each working group and the suggestion from the AGM 2024 for the working groups can be found [here](#). Below is a brief summary of the WGs work in 2024/2025.

WG Doctoral Training

The WG DT has had monthly meetings since November 2024. The WG has finalised a statement on supervision, which has been sent for input to the board. The statement was approved in June 2025 through an online vote. The statement can be found [here](#). The working group has given feedback on Eurodoc's statement on the Salzburg Recommendations.

WG Mental Health

The MH WG has held monthly meetings through the terms. The working group has developed a best practice workshop and has given this workshop on several occasions. The workshop will be given in person at the Conference in Copenhagen. Besides this, the working group has contributed to raising awareness about the importance of addressing mental health issues in academia. The working group is proposed to continue in 2025/2026.

WG Career Paths and working conditions

The CP WG has held monthly meetings. The WG are drafting a report where they have compared PhD salaries/stipends with the cost of living in 9 European countries.

WG Open Science

The working group has not been active in 2024/2025.

WG Equitable Opportunities and sustainable Research Cultures

The WG EO has held monthly meetings. The WG has drafted a policy paper on equitable opportunities based on Eurodocs previous work on the topic. The statement was sent to consultation in June. The working group has developed a workshop for the AGM.

WG Academic Integrity and Artificial Intelligence

The WG AI & AI has held monthly meetings since January of 2025. The WG has coordinated Eurodoc's input to the EC on training for early career researchers on the use of artificial intelligence. The input can be found [here](#).

5.4 External Communication

The board of Eurodoc and the external communication officer has established a strategy for the newsletter and for how to handle media contact.

The Eurodoc Newsletter is a central part of Eurodoc's communication activities, particularly towards external stakeholders, in 2024/2025 14 newsletters were sent out, serving as a vital tool to disseminate key information, updates, and achievements. Moreover, the management of the newsletter recipients have been improved by moving from a manually managed list into an email campaigning platform, including a self-signup form on the Eurodoc website and unsubscribe options in each of the newsletters sent. In March 2025 Eurodoc's board voted to limit Eurodoc's Social Media presence by leaving X - formerly known as Twitter. The decision was made as a reaction to how the development in the spring of 2025 in the US had affected stakeholders' presence at the platform. Eurodoc engaged in two larger outreach activities in 2024/2025. In December 2024 an ECR night where 22 ECRs presented their research was held and in the spring of 2025 Eurodoc has organised the campaign "[Voices of Ukrainian Scientist](#)" where more than 20 ECRs from Ukraine have been interviewed about their research and how the war has affected their research.

5.4.1 Social Media KPIs

From May 29, 2024 to July 15, 2025 Eurodoc's followership on social media grew as follows:

- **LinkedIn:** followers grew from 3955 (+21.87%) to 5064 followers;
 - there were 81,656 impressions; 1998 page views, 1148 unique visitors, 2900 reactions, 43 comments, 65 reposts.
- **Facebook:** followers grew from 7179 to 7311 (+1.8%) in the 2024/2025 term.
 - post reach: 35 194; post engagement: 4647; new page likes: 80;
- **Instagram** has 68 posts published in a year and the account has 350 followers altogether.

Need to:

- [To publish articles regularly on the Eurodoc website.](#) This has been achieved.
- [To publish the newsletter monthly and share information.](#) This has been achieved.
- [To continue Eurodoc's presence on Social Media.](#) This has been achieved.

5.5 25ECRs

In 2027 Eurodoc turns 25. This is planned to be celebrated on the 2/2-2027 with a half day hybrid conference in Brussels. To achieve this a task force consisting of former members of the board of Eurodoc has been established by the board. This task force will be responsible for putting together the program and identifying who should be invited. Furthermore, Eurodoc has a strategic target that by the AGM 2027 the organisation should have grown to 30 members and should be covering 25 countries. Thus, Eurodoc is well on track in terms of achieving. Leading up to the AGM 2025 Eurodoc received 4 membership applications. Furthermore, Eurodoc has been in contact with non-member organisations from other countries and the hope is that some will join Eurodoc in the coming years. Furthermore, a linkedin group for Eurodoc exists that we encourage all alumni to join.

Need to:

- [Make a task force for Eurodoc's 25 year anniversary celebration.](#) This has been achieved.

Nice to:

- [Plan extension of Eurodoc to 30 NAs and 25 countries by 2027.](#) This has been achieved.
- [Create a list of Eurodoc alumni to include former administration members and delegates.](#) This has been achieved.

6. Eurodoc Policy Work

The policy work of Eurodoc as described here consists of three parts. A part focusing on the training of ECRs, a part on Eurodoc statements and hearing contributions, and a part on Eurodoc representation.

6.1 Eurodoc Internal Trainings and Guides

Eurodoc is in the process of setting up a structure for the development of a comprehensive training of the Eurodoc administration and NA delegates. The training aims to equip as many ECRs as possible to participate in policy work, both within and outside of Eurodoc. The timeline for developing this training is 5 years, thus Eurodoc is still in the early phases of this work. These trainings will consist of elements that are internal (for Eurodoc' and NA delegates only) as well as external (for all interested). The internal part is supplemented by a part for members of the board.

To prepare this work and reduce reproduction of previous work, as a first step Eurodoc's drive has been cleaned up, and useful training and guides from past years has been identified. The current structure of Eurodoc's drive is described in an internal guide.

Eurodoc Guides and Trainings for Members of the Secretariat and Delegates

During 2024/2025 the board has updated the following guides; 1) Guide to delegates and 2) Guide to working group coordinators. The guide to delegates aims to inform new as well as old delegates about their rights and responsibilities as well as what they can expect as delegates in Eurodoc. The guides' to working group coordinators aims to do the same for new members of the secretariat focussing at working group coordinates. Both guides include a number of relevant links, including the one for the list of Eurodoc statements and policies. It would be recommended to expand both guides with a summary of these statements or highlight key statements.

Furthermore, the following two guides have been identified: A "[Guide for organising an AGM/Conference](#)" from 2013 and a "Guide for membership application ([2009](#))". It is recommended that both guides are updated.

For the ERA a summary document of its main components relevant for ECRs has been developed. Finally, for EHAE an internal training has been developed on the European Doctoral Education and its connection to the Bologna process.

Eurodoc ValDem

Eurodoc ValDem 2025 was a 14 week long course that ran in the spring 2025. The program provides a comprehensive overview of the democratic values of higher education and research in Europe. The [programme](#) included 17 online lectures given by prominent European organisations and experts, organized in three parts, followed up with three seminars. The participants could follow the lectures without participating in the ambassador programme. The lectures were usually attended live by 50-70 ECRs. The program came timely and was the first of its kind. Around 25 participants have concluded the full ambassador program at the time of writing, and around 25 are expected to do so during August. The material and recordings are available online at the platform "[Edoer](#)".

Need to:

- [Provide training on the landscape of EHEA and ERA](#). This has been achieved.

Nice to:

- [Set up the structure for a comprehensive training of the Eurodoc administration and NA delegates](#). This has been achieved.

6.2 Eurodoc Statements

Eurodoc maintains a list of statements as mandated by its statutes. This list is available to all delegates, but as of 2024/2025 all statements of Eurodoc have also been uploaded to Zenodo and is thus publicly available for everyone. During 2024/2025 the Eurodoc has released 14 statements, some based on previous statements and positions of Eurodoc and some addressing new policy issues and were thus released after a consultation process and voting process.

Besides this, the president and vice-president has given comments to the media more than 10 times. All requests for answering media are voted upon by the board. When time allows, the comments are shared internally in either the board or between the president, vice-president and secretary.

Many of Eurodoc's statements reflected the big focus there has been on the ongoing negotiations of the 10th Framework Program (FP10), the European Union's next budget - the Multi Financial Framework (MFF), and the upcoming European Research Act - the ERA Act and thus concerned the European Research Area. These statements reiterated the necessity of increasing the attractiveness of the academic career and ensuring that ECRs receive salaries that reflect their academic qualifications and experiences, furthermore these statements address the need for protecting and promoting academic freedom in Europe.

Another continuous topic throughout the year has been attacks on academic freedom and a general democratic backsliding. Eurodoc has not only addressed this issue through the statements on the ERA, but also by endorsing ALLEA's statements on combating attacks on Academic Freedom, and by calling for an increased focus on EHEAs academic values in doctoral education and strengthening the participation of ECRs in academic governance.

Hearing Responses at a European Level

Eurodoc has submitted input for four hearing processes conducted by the European Commission and one by the Council of Europe. The submissions for the European Commission were done in writing and it regards the following four "[Eurodoc response to "European Research Area – the new ERA 4 years on: achievements, lessons learnt and the way forward"](#)", "[Eurodoc Response on the Future of FP10 and ERC](#)", "[Eurodoc Statement on the Multi Financial Framework](#)" and "[Eurodoc Statement on AI in Science](#)". The submission for the Council of Europe was done by participation in an online in person consultation on "CoEs consultation meeting on its CM Recommendation on AI Literacy for Human Rights, Democracy and Social Agency".

Need to:

- [Policy brief on employment and financial conditions of ECRs](#). This has been achieved.
- [Policy paper on Representational Rights for Doctoral Candidates and Postdocs](#). This has been achieved.
- [Policy paper on Doctoral Supervision](#). This has been achieved.
- [Policy paper on making baseline conditions mandatory for public funding](#). This has been achieved.

Nice to:

- [Policy paper on Equitable Opportunities](#). The preparation has been done, and will be voted upon at the AGM.

Other

- [Policy responses and responses to media inquiries time permitting](#). This has been achieved.

6.3 Eurodoc Representational Work

Eurodoc engages with a number of stakeholders in the EHEA and ERA. The engagement varies from close collaborations to participation in events organised by such stakeholders. Eurodoc's president and vice-president meets regularly with representatives of MCAA, YAE, ICoRSA and ISE and in the coordination group of SH4.

6.3.1 Representing ECRs in Intergovernmental Organisations

In 2024/2025 Eurodoc have represented ECRs towards a number of European intergovernmental organisations such as the ERA (European Union), the EHEA and the Bologna follow up group (BFUG), the Council of Europe (CoE), in particular as an observer in the Council of Europe's Steering Committee on Education (CD-EDU). Though CoE and CD-EDU Eurodoc are currently represented in 4 sub-committees, ERA will likely be represented in 9 of the Policy Agendas and Actions. In BFUG Eurodoc could consider the work more actively through one or two working groups.

6.3.2 Engagement with University Alliances

Eurodoc has in 2024/2025 engaged directly with several university alliances, Science Europe, ALLEA, ENRIO and a number of other stakeholder organisations through its activities such as the ValDem programme and in CoARA and the CCA action.

6.3.3 As a Member of European Organisations

Eurodoc is a member of four different organisations: The Conference of International NGOs (CINGO), OING (the financial service allowing CINGO to carry out its work), the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), and the Initiative for Science Europe (ISE). The board will in 2024/2025 continue to actively represent Eurodoc in these 4 organisations and partake in their work through working groups and similar.

Eurodoc' has in 2024/2025 participated in both the autumn and spring session of **CINGO** and **OING**. Furthermore, members of the board of Eurodoc have represented Eurodoc in 3 of CINGOs committees.

In **CoARA** Eurodoc engages in several of the working groups and co-chairs in two of them CoARA WG EMCR the working group that focus on researcher assessment at the early and mid career stage and CoARA ERIP which focuses on the role and use of AI in research assessment.

As a member of the Initiative for Science in Europe. Eurodoc participated actively at ISEs general assembly in March, and through its two working groups where Eurodoc has 2 representatives in each of ISEs working groups.

Need to:

- [Participate in CD-EDU meetings](#). This has been achieved.
- [Participate in BFUG meetings](#). This has been achieved.
- [Maintain collaborations with ICoRSA, ISE, MCAA, and YAE](#). This has been achieved.
- [Participate in CoARA meetings and CoARA working group meetings](#). This has been achieved.

Nice to:

- [Establish stable collaborations with university alliances](#). This has been achieved.

7. Engagement in European Projects

7.1 DRU (2026 - 2029)

Eurodoc is a full partner to the Democratic Roles of Universities (DRU): Practicing Democratic Values in Science, Education, Civic Engagement and Governance (DRU) project, DRU's objective is to find new ways that universities can strengthen the democratic fabric of society. The DRU project will start in the first half of 2026.

7.2 IANUS (2025 - 2028)

Eurodoc is an associated partner of "Integrative MSCA Achievements and Networks for Unified Strategies" (IANUS). The main goal of the project is to understand the impact of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) on beneficiaries and to develop tools that allow to maximise their strategic impact. The focus is on three areas: the MSCA's contribution to the EU missions, on boosting cross-sector collaboration, and on improving support for researchers - especially ECRs and researchers from universities with less resources - in terms of training and skills both in preparing grant applications and in regards to AI literacy and the ethical use of AI in research. Eurodoc contributes to the project by bringing the ECRs perspective to the project and by bringing contact to ECRs.

7.3 Open4UA (2023 - 2026)

Eurodoc is a [partner](#) in the Open Science for Ukrainian Higher Education System ([Open4UA](#)) Erasmus+ project. The project started in January 2023 and will end in October 2026. The main goal of the Open Science for Ukrainian Higher Education System (Open4UA) project, is to promote the growth of Ukraine's knowledge economy for post-war recovery by reforming by prioritizing open science through legislative measures, through research assessment practices and through institutional practices and policies.

7.4 OPTIMA (2021 - 2025)

Eurodoc was a full partner in the Open Practices, Transparency and Integrity for Modern Academia ([OPTIMA](#)) project that implements Open Science practices in Ukraine to improve the quality of National higher education services. The role of Eurodoc in the project is to advise on all the project activities, assist in the creation of an international online community of peer reviewers, and act as speakers and workshop leaders at project events. OPTIMA was prolonged for one year till mid-January 2025. In the reporting period, Eurodoc representatives delivered presentations and led workshops at the OPTIMA events in Nice (France) and Graz (Austria). Also, Eurodocers took part in shaping the community of peer reviewers at [Peers.International](#), project's open peer review platform.

7.5 OPUS (2022 - 2025)

The main goal of the Open and Universal Science (OPUS) project is to develop a system that incentivises and rewards researchers to practise open science. With a specific focus on reforming the research(ers) assessment system, the project includes a comprehensive state of the art on literature and initiatives for open science, the design of a set of interventions, the development of realistic indicators and metrics for open science and test them, and the collection of stakeholders' feedback.

7.6 SECURE 1 (2023 - 2025)

Eurodoc was a full partner in the "[SECURE - Sustainable Careers for Researchers Empowerment](#)", aimed to create, trial, implement, and mainstream a common Research Career Framework. The original plan was overrun by the publication of *the Council Recommendation on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe (EC)*. The consortium effectively collaborated in creating a [Researchers Career Framework](#) that translates the Council recommendations into living principles and implementable practical suggestions. Furthermore,

the project led to the development of 9 basic principles that are needed to inform any [tenure track-like models](#). Along this core work, Eurodoc participated in the drafting of the initial policy briefs, and in many dissemination and outreach activities of the project.

7.7 SECURE 2 (2025 - 2029)

Eurodoc is also a full partner to the Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment 2 (SECURE2) project, that is dedicated to pilot and implement recommendations from the European Framework for Research Careers to improve research career progression and mobility within research-performing organizations and research-funding organizations.

7.8 Open Research Europe (2021 -)

Eurodoc is an expert partner in the "[Open Research Europe](#)" (ORE) project, an Open Access Publishing Platform, launched in the spring of 2021 by the European Commission. The platform is a significant step toward Open Science in Europe as it promotes preprints, open peer review, reproducibility, etc, and the role of Eurodoc is to ensure that the voice of ECRs is heard during its development and implementation.

The European Council of Doctoral
Candidates and Junior Researchers

8 Special Thanks From the President

I first interacted with Eurodoc in the spring of 2020, I reached out on behalf of my national association with questions about an annual questionnaire that had left me quite confused. I left the meeting feeling that here I had met someone who I would love to work with. It became the first of many of such meetings in Eurodoc.

First and foremost, there is no Eurodoc without the people that engage in it either directly or through one of its members. In that sense Eurodoc's National Associations are the backbone of the organisation, and I want to thank all of the delegates and other representatives that I have worked and collaborated with over the years, for your trust and support. Through Eurodoc I have had the privilege and curse to be a part of organising four of Eurodoc's conferences and AGMs. Behind the scenes, it takes a lot of will and work, and I am thankful to all of those in LSJR, SFS/SFS-DK, SNPA, MA and PAND for their commitment and contributions to making all of these conferences and AGMs happen. I know from my own engagement in Sweden how much time and work goes into this, not only at a European level, but also at a national and local level. With Alex, Agbor, Irina, Laura, Linnea, Karl, Maria, Matt, Sanskriti, Sara and Topias who all have been active in Eurodoc during my time as well as in SFS/DK or SNPA I had the chance to be part of some amazing teams and collaborations.

Just as Eurodoc does not work without its members it also does not work without its administration. The working group coordinators, the communication team, and the board – without them there is no Eurodoc. Many of the projects we work on today started out in discussions in working groups 3-5 years ago. To the former board members who all at some point during this past year have given me or others in the board of Eurodoc their time, knowledge and help: Aga, Aleksandra, Beata, Danilla, Devris, Eva, Farouk, Filomena, Iryna, Gareth, Guilia, Joanna, Olek, Marianna, Mathias, Miia, Sara, and Sebastian a common denominator is that they remain more than willing to continue to help support Eurodoc and its mission - and for me personally that has meant the world.

To the people from the MCAA, YAE, ICoRSA and ISE. Whether it has been in the projects like OPUS and SECURE or in endless online meetings on the topic of MFF, FP10 and ERA Act your commitments are impressive. Carolina, Irena, Martin, Moniek, Monica, Gordon, Tereza, Scott, Katalin Gian and of course Mostafa it has been a pleasure, privilege, and a lot of fun to work with you.

For Eurodoc to be able to advocate for the past three years that the EU must continue to support the higher education and the research sector in Ukraine is contingent on engagement and commitments of ECRs from Ukraine as well as the rest of Europe. To everyone who has engaged with me in Eurodoc's taskforce or other work regarding support for Ukraine – a huge thank you! Especially to Olesia, Anastasiia, Laryssa, and many others from YSC who welcomed me and Sebastian Dahle in Kyiv in the summer of 2023; to Olek, Anna and Sebastian for all the work you have put into this on behalf of Eurodoc, and to the ECRs that shared their stories in the campaign "Voices of Ukrainian Science".

This year has for me of course been special and to the entire team I just want to say thank you! To project officers, working group coordinators, and communication officers Agnieszka, Aleksandra, Anastasiia, Anthony, Gledson, Joanna, Khrystyna, and Viktoriia – thanks for going over and over again and again and again. To Anna and Linnea thanks for coordinating the communication team and secretariat and together with Eurodoc's board members Karl, Magali, Manca, and Norbert for all the laughter, for the discussions, and reflections. To Hannah and Nicola, Eurodoc's incredible secretary and vice-president, thanks for all the Sunday evenings filled with coffee.

I hope the above shows how many people it takes to make Eurodoc work. From that first meeting, for me personally, it was and is a team sport and while some roles are more visible it only works because of all the collective and often invisible work. Though I was never the biggest fan of Eurodoc's annual questionnaire it was what lured me in. So thank you Mathias for taking your time to introduce me to Eurodoc in the spring of 2020 and for all the friendships and work that it brought with it.

9 New Eurodoc Statements

Date	Event	Ref number	Place/form
2024-10-06	Eurodoc Response to "European Research Area – the new ERA 4 years on: achievements, lessons learnt and the way forward"	Ref: 2024-2	https://zenodo.org/records/13890522
2024-10-11	Eurodoc Response on the Future of FP10 and ERC	Ref: 2024-3	https://zenodo.org/records/13919031
2024-10-17	Eurodoc and MCAA Response on the Horizon Europe Interim Evaluation Report	Ref: 2024-4	https://zenodo.org/records/13944737
2025-02-03	Eurodoc Response on "A Competitiveness Compass for the EU"	Ref: 2025-1	https://zenodo.org/records/14796000
2025-02-23	Eurodoc endorses ALLEA's Statement on Threats to Academic Freedom and International Research Collaboration in the United States	Ref: 2025-2	NA
2025-05-06	Eurodoc Statement on the Multi Financial Framework	Ref: 2025-3	https://zenodo.org/records/15353356
2025-05-25	Eurodoc Endorses ALLEA's Statement on Continued Attacks on Academic Freedom	Ref: 2025-4	https://zenodo.org/records/15544902
2025-05-25	Eurodoc Statement on the 20th Anniversary of the Salzburg Recommendations	Ref: 2025-5	https://zenodo.org/records/15879253
2025-05-26	Eurodoc Statement on Employment and Financial Conditions of ECRS	Ref: 2025-6	https://zenodo.org/records/15522204
2025-05-26	Eurodoc Statement on Representational Rights of ECRs	Ref: 2025-7	https://zenodo.org/records/15522244
2025-05-30	Report Eurodoc Postdoc Survey	Ref: 2025-8	https://zenodo.org/records/15756208
2025-06-05	Eurodoc Statement on AI in Science	Ref: 2025-9	https://zenodo.org/records/15768274
2025-07-01	Eurodoc Statement on Doctoral Supervision	Ref: 2025-10	https://zenodo.org/records/15784650
2025-07-22	Eurodoc and MCAA statement on the ERA Act	Ref: 2025-11	https://zenodo.org/records/16309750
2025-08-09	<i>Eurodoc statement on Equitable opportunities</i>	Ref: 2025-12	https://zenodo.org/records/16921002
2025-08-09	<i>Eurodoc second CoARA Action Plan</i>	Ref: 2025-13	https://zenodo.org/records/16921111
2025-08-09	<i>Eurodoc Gender Equality and Anti-Discrimination Plan vs 2</i>	Ref: 2025-14	https://zenodo.org/records/16920759
2025-08-09	<i>Eurodoc Statement in Support of the European Commission's Suggestion to Suspend Israel from Parts of Horizon Europe</i>	Ref: 2025-15	https://zenodo.org/records/16921133
2025-08-09	<i>Eurodoc Annual Report 2024/2025</i>	Ref: 2025-0	

10 Eurodoc Press Coverage

Name of Eurodoc representative	Platform	Date	Link
Pil Maria Saugmann	Research Professional News	2024.11.07	Link
Norbert Bencze	GILE Journal of Skills Development	2025.02.02	Link
Pil Maria Saugmann	Research Professional News	2025.02.20	Link
Pil Maria Saugmann	Research Professional News	2025.03.06	Link
Nicola Dengo	Science Business	2025.03.27	Link
Pil Maria Saugmann	Research Professional News	2025.04.02	Link
Pil Maria Saugmann and Hannah Schoch	Research Professional News	2025.04.15	Link
Pil Maria Saugmann	Research Professional News	2025.07.03	Link
Eurodoc and MCAA	ERA Portal Austria	2025.07.28	Link
Pil Maria Saugmann	Nature career	<i>To be published</i>	

11 List of Eurodoc Activities in 2024/2025

Eurodoc representatives contributed to many conferences, meetings, and events. We tried to list all of them in the table below. You can find short descriptions and further information on each meeting [here](#).

Name of Eurodoc representative	Event	Date	Place/form
Sebastian Dahle, Aleksandra Lewandowska	ESOF	11.-15.06.2024	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann	SNPA intro day	12.06.2024	online
Pil Maria Saugmann	CD-EDU Steering committee	11.-12.06.2024	in person
Pil Maria Saugmann	SGroup	19.06.2024	online
Nicola Dengo	Cooperate Project for ERA	25.06.2024	online
Nicola Dengo	ERA Talents	25.06.2024	online
Hannah Schoch	AESIS	26.-28.06.2024	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann	ReMO Workshop	02.07.2024	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann	CoE- 3 Forum of History Education	08.07.2024	Online
Sara Wilhammar, Aleksandra Lewandowska	REMO + Eurodoc seminar		Online
Hannah Schoch	CD-EDU and UNESCO	5.-6.09.2024	online
Oleksandr Berezko	Annual conference of Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association	12.-16.09.2024	online
Sebastian Dahle, Norbert Bencze	ERA conference "European Research Area:	18.09.2024	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann	CD-EDU Higher Education Subgroup	18.-19.09.2024	In person
Karl Kilbo Edlund	Hamburg Science Summit	19.09.2024	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann	EXIT Meeting	20.09.2024	In person
Norbert Bencze	Generation	30.09.2024	Online
Karl Kilbo Edlund, Nicola Dengo	COOPERATE	23.09.2024	Online
Pil Maria Saugmann	GS-HIST- COE	25.09.2024	In person
Aleksandra Lewandowska	BFUG Meeting	26.-27.09.2024	In person
Magali Weissgerber, Nicola Dengo	YERUN - SECURE meeting	16.09.2024	Online
Pil Maria Saugmann, Hannah Schoch	CD-EDU Meeting	09.-11.10.2024	In person

Pil Maria Saugmann (IRL), Magali Weissgerber, (O) Norbert Benzce, (O) Manca Lunder (O)	CINGO Meeting	14.-16.10.2024	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann	CoE meeting	17.-18.10.2024	In person
Hannah Schoch	LERU paper launch communicating with integrity	22.10.2024	online
Hannah Schoch	YSC Conference	25.10.2024	online
Pil Maria Saugmann	LERU	25.-26.10.2024	In person
Magali Weissgerber	CoE (CITEH)	14.10.2024	online
Sebastian Dahle	SNSF	05.-06.11.2024	In person
Nicola Dengo	Community of practice (CoP) for recruitment to academia and the non-academic public sector.	11.11.2024	Online
Pil Maria Saugmann, Agnieszka Zyra	Opus General Meeting	12.-13.11.2024	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann, Agnieszka Zyra	Rethinking Research Assessment" - keynote speaker	14.11.2024	In person
Hannah Schoch	Academic Freedom in Action	13.-14.11.2024	in person
Pil Maria Saugmann	GS-HIST- COE	14.11.2024	Online
Hannah Schoch	EQAF 2024	15.-16.11.2024	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann, Hannah Schoch, Norbert Benzce	DOSZ – Academic Competitiveness	18.11.2024	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann, Hannah Schoch, Norbert Benzce, Nicola Dengo	World Science Forum	19.-22.11.2024	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann, Sebastian Dahle	Optima, Lviv	21.11.2024	In person/online
Nicola Dengo	Italian Senate	26.11.2024	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann	Euraxess	26.11.2024	In person
Magali Weissgerber	EC	28.11.2024	online
Nicola Dengo	COST	03.12.2024	In person
Sebastian Dahle	INSPIRE-ERA	04.12.2024	Online
Pil Maria Saugman	CD-EDU Steering committee	9.12.2024	In person
Karl Kilbo Edlund	MSCA Planning 1st meeting	13.12.2024	In person
Norbert Bencze	PENKALA Meeting	27.12.2024	Online
Hannah Schoch	CoE: Ad Hoc Working Group on Automatic Recognition	15.01.2025	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann	CoE: CDEDU Bureau	16.01.2025	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann	4th Forum of History Planning	23.01.2025	In person
Aleksandra Lewandowska, Sara Willhammar	11th Virtual Winter School on Computational Chemistry 28/01/2025	28.01.2025	Online
Pil Maria Saugmann	STOA	05.02.2025	In person
Aleksandra Lewandowska	BFUG	24.-25.02.2025	In person
Hannah Schoch	CoE: Ad Hoc Working Group on Automatic Recognition	26.02.2025	online
Karl Kilbo Edlund	European Universities meeting	27.02.2025	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann, Hannah Schoch	Meeting with EUA-CDE	28.02.2025	Online
Nicola Dengo	Community of practice (CoP)	28.02.2025	Online
Agnieszka Zyra, Norbert Bencze, Aleksandra Lewandowska, Mathias Schrojner, Eva Hatkova	SECURE Meeting	06.-07.03.2025	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann	CoE: CDEDU Subgroup on HE	06.-07.03.2025	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann, Nicola Dengo	Meeting with COIMBRA	11.03.2025	Online
Pil Maria Saugmann	LERU	14.03.2025	Online
Hannah Schoch, Pil Maria Saugmann	CoE: CDEDU Plenary	17.-19.03.2025	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann, Norbert Bencze, Agnieszka Zyra	MCAA	20.-22.03.2025	In person

Pil Maria Saugmann, Nicola Dengo	ISE General assembly	25.-26.03.2025	In person
Norbert Bencze	UNESCO	25.-26.03.2025	In person
Hannah Schoch	Trust in Science	27.03.2025	In person
Magali Weissgerber	Doctoral Education in Universities of Applied Sciences	24.03.2025	Online
Pil Maria Saugmann, Agnieszka Zyra, Magali Weisgerber	CoARA EMCR WG	27.03.2025	online
Pil Maria Saugmann	MSCA Conference Planning	28.03.2025	online
Hannah Schoch, Magali Weissgerber	ANDÉS	31.03.2025	Online
Magali Weissgerber	The Guild of European Research-Intensive Universities	01.04.2025	Online
Hannah Schoch	IANUS kick-off meeting	03.-04.04.2025	In person
Norbert Bencze	Education and Migration	03.04.2025	Online
Pil Maria Saugmann	ERA Forum	04.04.2025	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann	CINGO meeting	07-09.04.2025	In person
Pil Maria Saugmann, Magali Weisgerber	CoARA EMCR WG	24.04.2025	online
Pil Maria Saugmann	MSCA Conf planning	29.04.2025	online
Linnea Carlsson	CoEs consultation meeting	06.05.2025	online
Norbert Bencze	Trust in Science	13.-14.05.2025	online
Pil Maria Saugmann	AIOLA	15.05.2025	online
Magali Weisgerber	CoARA EMCR WG	15.05.2025	online
Pil Maria Saugmann	CoARA WG Co-chair meeting	15.05.2025	online
Karl Kilbo Edlund	EPAN	20.-21.05.2025	in person
Pil Maria Saugmann	MLE	22.05.2025	in person
Pil Maria Saugmann, Hannah Schoch	Meeting with NuWiss	21.05.-2025	online
Aleksandra Lewandowska	PhD Success	22.05.2025	online
Norbert Bencze	Integrating gender and intersectionality in research: from policy to practice	28.05.2025	online
Pil Maria Saugmann	AF Forum	02.-04.06.2025	in person
Hannah Schoch	EUA-CDE	04.06.2025	in person
Norbert Bencze, Agnieszka Zyra	Open4UA	03-06.06.2025	in person
Pil Maria Saugmann, Magali Weisgerber	CoARA EMCR WG	05.05.2025	online
Pil Maria Saugmann, Norbert Bencze, Anna Pavelieva	4th Forum on History Education	11-13.06.2025	in person
Linnea Carlsson	FOD - Technopolis	17.06.2025	online
Magali Weisgerber	CoARA General Assembly	23.06.2025	online
Pil Maria Saugmann	Meeting with DocSoc	23.06.2025	online
Pil Maria Saugmann	ELKANA Conference	24.-25.06.2025	in person
Hannah Schoch	DRU first meeting	25.06.2025	online
Nicola Dengo	ERA Day, University of Padova	27.06.2025	in person
Pil Maria Saugmann	CoE: CDEDU Bureau	02.07.2025	in person
Hannah Schoch	CoE: Ad Hoc Working Group on Automatic Recognition	03.07.2025	in person
Karl Kilbo Edlund	CoE: WG Students' Rights Charter	03.-04.07.2025	in person
Pil Maria Saugmann, Agnieszka Zyra	UNESCO	07.-08.07.2025	in person
Magali Weissgerber	ICoRSA	08.07.2025	online
Pil Maria Saugmann, Agnieszka Zyra	OPUS	09-10.07.2025	in person